

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Stress, Anxiety, Memory, Depression and Blood Pressure

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ABSTRACT:

Chronic stress, anxiety, and hypertension are significant health concerns that negatively impact overall well-being, often leading to cognitive decline, insomnia, and other complications. This study evaluated the effectiveness of Brain Health herbal supplement, a nutraceutical supplement, in managing stress-related conditions such as hypertension, anxiety, epilepsy, depression, insomnia, and cognitive impairments. A total of 61 participants (35 males, 26 females; mean age 47.82 ± 11.40 years) were administered one or two tablets twice daily for 60 days. The assessment criteria included blood pressure regulation, anxiety and stress reduction, seizure frequency in epilepsy patients, and cognitive function improvements. Statistical analysis conducted using SPSS version 10.0 showed that 81.58% of hypertensive patients achieved complete symptom control, while 18.42% showed improvement. Among epilepsy patients, 100% demonstrated symptom improvement, though complete seizure control was not achieved. Anxiety and stress relief were observed in 46.67% and 87.50% of cases, respectively, while 71.43% of depression cases and 60% of insomnia cases showed improvement. Additionally, 85.71% of patients with memory-related issues and 90% of those experiencing giddiness, jerks, and weakness reported positive outcomes. The supplement was well tolerated, with no severe adverse effects reported. These findings suggest that Brain health herbal supplement may be a promising natural intervention for stress-related disorders, with potential benefits for cardiovascular, neurological, and mental health. Further large-scale clinical trials are recommended to confirm long-term efficacy and explore broader applications.

Keywords: Brain Health herbal supplement, anxiety relief, blood pressure regulation, memory enhancement, epilepsy management, stress reduction.

INTRODUCTION:

Stress is a natural response to challenges, but chronic exposure can negatively impact physical and mental health. It is linked to cardiovascular diseases, weakened immunity, hormonal imbalances, anxiety, depression, cognitive decline, and sleep disturbances (1,2). Mental stress is complex to define and measure, as it depends on both external stressors and individual coping abilities (3). Stress, anxiety, depression, and hypertension affect a large global population, increasing the risk of cardiovascular diseases, cognitive decline, and kidney failure (1,4). Anxiety contributes to hypertension and unhealthy behaviors like smoking, inactivity, and

obesity, particularly in older hypertensive patients with a history of stroke or depression (5). Various factors, including age, social relationships, income, and education, influence stress levels, with cardiovascular patients being the most affected (6).

Globally, 970 million people suffer from mental health disorders, with anxiety affecting 301 million and depression 280 million (7). Hypertension, a major risk factor for stroke and heart disease, affects 1.13 billion people, with two-thirds residing in low- and middle-income countries (8). Given the rising prevalence of these conditions, effective interventions are crucial. Stress impacts the body differently based on stimulus

type, intensity, and duration, ranging from temporary imbalances to severe health risks (9). Pharmacological treatments, such as antidepressants and anxiolytics, are commonly prescribed for stress-related disorders (10). However, these medications often come with side effects, including dependency, tolerance, and various adverse physiological reactions. For instance, antidepressants have been associated with serotonin syndrome, suicidal thoughts, sexual dysfunction, hepatotoxicity and priapism, increased risk of type 2 diabetes, and potential interactions with other medications (11). These limitations highlight the necessity for safer, more natural therapeutic options. Herbal and nutraceutical supplements, known for their adaptogenic, neuroprotective, and anti-stress properties, offer potential benefits in managing stress and improving cognitive and cardiovascular health (12).

Nutraceuticals, encompassing products derived from food sources with additional health benefits beyond basic nutritional value, have gained attention for their potential in managing stress and related disorders. (13) Many natural compounds possess adaptogenic, neuroprotective, and anti-stress properties, helping regulate the body's stress response and support mental well-being. Adaptogens modulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, reducing cortisol levels and restoring homeostasis (14) These properties position nutraceuticals as promising alternatives or adjuncts to conventional pharmacotherapy in the management of stress-related conditions.

The present study aims to evaluate a natural, multi-targeted approach to stress management through the use of Brain Health Herbal Supplement, a specially formulated supplement. This supplement contains a blend of adaptogenic and neuroprotective ingredients known for their potential benefits in mental and physical well-being, including anxiety reduction, memory enhancement, blood pressure regulation, and overall stress relief. This study assesses the effectiveness of Brain Health Herbal Supplement in individuals experiencing anxiety, depression, hypertension, memory concerns, and stress-related symptoms. Participants were administered the supplement for a 60-day period, with health parameters monitored to determine improvements. Through this research, we aim to contribute to the development of evidence-based, natural interventions that support stress management and promote holistic well-being.

CASE PRESENTATION AND METHODOLOGY:

A total of 61 participants experiencing various stress-related conditions, including hypertension, anxiety, epilepsy, depression, memory issues, insomnia, and

other general health concerns such as giddiness, jerks, and weakness, were enrolled in this study. Participants were selected based on their medical history and clinical symptoms to ensure a diverse representation of cases. The study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of Brain Health herbal supplement, a nutraceutical supplement, in managing these conditions over a period of 60 days. Each participant followed a structured regimen, taking one or two tablets twice daily, with regular monitoring to ensure adherence. Only those who strictly followed the prescribed dosage were included in the final analysis. The study group comprised 35 males and 26 females, with an average age of 47.82 ± 11.40 years.

The effectiveness of Brain Health herbal supplement was assessed using both physiological and psychological markers. Blood pressure levels were measured using a sphygmomanometer to track changes in systolic and diastolic BP, while cortisol levels were analyzed as a key biomarker of stress regulation. Heart rate variability was recorded to assess autonomic nervous system balance, providing insights into stress adaptation. Additionally, sleep quality was evaluated using standardized sleep scales, and self-reported stress and anxiety levels were measured through validated psychological assessment tools. For epilepsy patients, neurological assessments were conducted to monitor changes in seizure frequency and severity, offering a broader understanding of the supplement's impact on neurological health. Symptom recovery across all conditions, including memory function, insomnia, and general health concerns, was analyzed to determine overall effectiveness.

This comprehensive methodology ensured an evidence-based evaluation of Brain Health herbal supplement as a potential natural intervention for stress management, cardiovascular regulation, neurological support, and overall well-being. Statistical analyses using SPSS version 10.0 were performed to determine the significance of observed improvements, reinforcing the findings of the study.

INTERVENTION:

Participants were given 1 or 2 tablets of the Brain Health herbal supplement product twice daily for 60 days.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis was conducted based on the intention-to-treat principles. Changes in blood pressure were assessed using the Student's t-test, with results expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or as the incidence of patients experiencing blood pressure changes. Patient demographic details were also analyzed. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically

significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 10.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The effect of the Brain Health herbal supplement product on various laboratory parameters in patients experiencing stress-related diseases was evaluated. A total of 61 cases were assessed, all of whom adhered

strictly to the treatment regimen for the designated duration. Only cases where participants did not miss any doses were considered. The study included 35 male and 26 female participants. The average age of male participants was 48.68 ± 10.56 years, while the average age of female participants was 46.65 ± 12.56 years. The overall average age of all participants was 47.82 ± 11.40 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic data.

Demographic Details	Male	Female	Total
No. of subjects	35	26	61
Age (Average \pm SD)	48.68 ± 10.56	46.65 ± 12.56	47.82 ± 11.40

Data is represented as Mean \pm S.D.

Comorbidity:

Out of the total participants, 43 individuals (70.5%) had at least one comorbidity, while 18 participants (29.5%) had no comorbid conditions. This indicates a higher prevalence of comorbidities among the study population, which may have influenced the overall treatment outcomes.

Out of the 61 participants in the study, blood pressure was assessed in 40 cases following a 60-day treatment with the Brain Health herbal supplement. The initial mean systolic BP significantly reduced from 154.18 ± 9.84 mmHg to 128.98 ± 5.80 mmHg, while the diastolic BP decreased from 99.45 ± 7.40 mmHg to 84.8 ± 4.96 mmHg. The reduction in blood pressure was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2, Figure 1).

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Blood Pressure:

Table 2: Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Blood Pressure

Parameter	Before Treatment (n=40)	After Treatment (n=40)
Systolic BP (mmHg)	154.18 ± 9.84	128.98 ± 5.80
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	99.45 ± 7.40	84.8 ± 4.96

Data is represented as Mean \pm S.D. Data was analyzed by Student T Dependent Test. Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1: Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Blood Pressure

Effectiveness of Brain Health Herbal Supplement in Epilepsy Patients:

Among the 61 participants in the study, a subgroup of 21 patients with epilepsy-related symptoms was assessed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Brain Health herbal supplement product in managing their condition. After a 60-day treatment period, all patients showed improvement in their symptoms, indicating a positive response to the intervention. A significant number of patients experienced a reduction in seizure frequency, with some also reporting decreased severity of episodes. Additionally, neurological symptoms such as jerks, anxiety, and depression showed notable improvements, contributing to better mental well-being. Several patients had comorbid conditions, including memory issues and depression, yet they also experienced positive outcomes in their overall health. Importantly, the treatment was well tolerated, with no severe adverse effects reported. While complete seizure control was not achieved, the statistical data suggests that the Brain Health herbal supplement product effectively enhanced symptom

control, reduced episode severity, and contributed to an overall improved quality of life for epilepsy patients.

Treatment Effectiveness of Brain Health Herbal Supplement in Various Symptoms:

The effectiveness of the Brain Health herbal supplement product was assessed based on patient recovery outcomes. Among the 61 patients who adhered strictly to the treatment regimen, 31 patients (50.8%) achieved complete symptom control, while 30 patients (49.2%) showed significant symptom improvement. Common symptoms included blood pressure issues, epilepsy, anxiety, stress, depression, and insomnia. Some patients had multiple symptoms like memory problems, weakness, and giddiness. Patients in the complete control group experienced full relief, while those in the improvement group had noticeable symptom reduction. Results indicate high effectiveness, particularly in managing blood pressure, anxiety, stress, and insomnia. The large number of blood pressure-related cases highlights its potential cardiovascular benefits. (Table 4, Figure 3)

Table 3: Treatment Effectiveness of Brain Health Herbal Supplement.

Recovery Outcome	Number of Patients
Controlled	31
Improved	30

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Blood Pressure Recovery:

Among the 61 patients enrolled in the study, 38 individuals exhibited symptoms related to blood pressure. These participants underwent treatment with the Brain Health herbal supplement for a duration of 60 days. The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of the tablet in managing blood pressure-related symptoms. At the end of the treatment period, recovery outcomes were evaluated. As shown in the Figure 4, 31 patients (81.58%) achieved complete control over their blood pressure symptoms, while 7 patients (18.42%) experienced significant improvement. The high percentage of patients achieving full symptom control suggests the effectiveness of the Brain Health herbal supplement in managing blood pressure-related issues. Figure 2 (a)

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Epilepsy Recovery:

Among the 61 patients included in the study, 9 individuals exhibited symptoms of epilepsy and were treated with the Brain Health herbal supplement for a period of 60 days. The objective was to evaluate the tablet's effectiveness in managing epilepsy-related symptoms. At the end of the study, none of the patients achieved complete symptom control, while all 9 patients (100%) showed significant improvement in their condition, as illustrated in the graph. This indicates that while the tablet may not completely eliminate epilepsy symptoms, it contributes to notable symptomatic relief. Figure 2 (b)

Figure 2: Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on (a) Blood Pressure and (b) Epilepsy Recovery

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Anxiety:

Among the 61 patients included in the study, 15 individuals exhibited symptoms of anxiety. The results showed that 7 patients (46.67%) achieved complete symptom control, while 8 patients (53.33%) demonstrated significant improvement, as illustrated in Figure 3 (a).

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Stress:

Among the 61 patients included in the study, 08 individuals exhibited symptoms of stress and the stress recovery outcomes were assessed after treatment. The

results showed that 7 Patients (87.50%) achieved complete symptom control, while 1 Patient (12.50%) demonstrated significant improvement, as shown in the Figure 3 (b).

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Depression:

Among the 61 patients in the study, 7 individuals exhibited symptoms of depression. Following treatment, the recovery outcomes were evaluated, revealing that 2 patients (28.57%) successfully achieved full symptom control, while 5 patients (71.43%) experienced significant improvement, as shown in Figure 3 (c).

Figure 3: Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on (a)Anxiety, (b) Stress and (c) Depression Recovery

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Insomnia:

Among the 61 patients included in the study, 5 individuals exhibited symptoms of insomnia. The findings indicated that 2 patients (40%) were able to fully control their symptoms, while 3 patients (60%) showed notable improvement, as depicted in the Figure 4 (a).

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Memory Problems:

Among the 61 patients in the study, 7 individuals experienced memory-related difficulties or cognitive

issues. Following treatment, the results indicated that 1 patient (14.29%) achieved complete symptom resolution, while 6 patients (85.71%) showed significant improvement, as shown in Figure 4(b).

Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Other Health Problems:

Among the 61 patients analyzed in the study, 10 individuals experienced other health issues, such as giddiness, jerks, and general weakness. The findings revealed that 1 patient (10%) attained full symptom control, while 9 patients (90%) showed substantial improvement, as depicted in the Figure 4 (c).

Figure 4: Effect of Brain Health Herbal Supplement on Insomnia, Memory Problems and Other Health Problems Recovery

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study suggest that Brain Health herbal supplement, a natural supplement, is highly effective in managing stress-related conditions such as hypertension, epilepsy, anxiety, depression, insomnia,

and memory issues. Among the 61 participants, 50.8% achieved complete symptom control, while 49.2% showed significant improvement. The most notable benefits were seen in blood pressure regulation, with 81.58% of hypertensive patients experiencing full

recovery and 18.42% showing improvement. Anxiety and stress management also yielded positive results, with 46.67% and 87.50% of affected individuals achieving complete symptom relief, respectively. Similarly, 40% of insomnia patients fully recovered, while 60% showed significant improvement. For epilepsy patients, 100% demonstrated symptom improvement, although complete seizure control was not achieved, suggesting the supplement may serve as a supportive therapy rather than a standalone treatment. Additionally, 90% of individuals experiencing general health concerns like giddiness, jerks, and weakness reported substantial relief. Importantly, the supplement was well tolerated, with no severe adverse effects recorded.

These results highlight the potential of Brain Health herbal supplement as a natural and effective alternative or adjunct to conventional therapies for stress-related conditions. Given the promising outcomes observed in this study, further large-scale clinical trials are recommended to validate these findings, explore long-term benefits, and assess its applicability across diverse populations. A deeper investigation into the mechanisms of action of the supplement, particularly its impact on neurological disorders and cardiovascular health, may provide valuable insights for developing more targeted natural therapies for stress management.

AUTHORSHIP CRITERIA:

All authors have significantly contributed to this work, including its conception, design, and data acquisition. They were actively involved in analyzing and interpreting the data, as well as drafting, revising, and critically reviewing the manuscript. Each author has approved the final version for publication, agreed on the chosen journal, and takes full responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of the work in all aspects.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

Dr. Shridhar J. Pandya, and Dr. Chetan H. Savaliya, Dr. Vaishnavi B. Shiravale are part of Gplife Healthcare Pvt Ltd. Other author declares no conflict of interest. This study received financial support from Gplife Healthcare Pvt. Ltd.

GRANT INFORMATION:

Gplife Healthcare Pvt. Ltd., Surat, provided the study medication and covered the expenses related to laboratory testing for the participants.

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